

Data Science, AI and Citizen Innovation

A think tank policymaking approach

Presentation outline

- Transparency: declassification of diplomatic cables - FGV & Columbia University
- Policymaking in Energy and Facilities: preventing network failures for the Rio de Janeiro Power Distribution Company - FGV & Light
- Cultural Analytics - exploration space @ Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (ACDH)

HISTORY LAB

Documents

Data

History as Data Science

We turn documents into data and develop tools to explore history.

History, CS and Math

- A Research & Development Team of Data Scientists, Social Scientists, Engineers, and Web Developers, and Stakeholders

The Biggest Database of Declassified Documents

- **The Foreign Relations of the United States (1945-1980).** A curated collection of the ~80,000 most important declassified documents selected by State Department historians with access to every government department and agency.
- **The State Department Central Foreign Policy Files (1973-1978).** 1.7 million State Department Cables and metadata from ~500,000 more still classified cables and documents delivered by diplomatic pouch.
- **Henry Kissinger Telephone Conversations (1973-1976).** 4.5 thousand transcripts of Kissinger Telephone Conversations during his tenure as Secretary of State.
- **The Hillary Clinton Emails (2009-2012).** As of November release, 16,246 email chains with a total of 40,737 individual messages
- **Other Collections To Come:**
 - President's Daily Briefs
 - FBI "Vault" of FOIA'ed documents
 - NATO Archives
 - Aramis (UK Foreign Office Cables 1992-2000)

Topic Modeling for “off-topic” Communications

Extracting Embedded Social Networks

This is hard

This is easy

- (...)
- **CLOSE ASSOCIATES OF GENSCHER** HAVE TOLD US THAT **HE**
- IS VERY TIRED OF THE COALITION AND THAT HE HAS PARTICULARLY RESENTED **SCHMIDT'S** TENDENCY TO ACT WITHOUT CONSULTATION DURING THE ELECTION CAMPAIGN.
- (...)

✘ 1.7 million

Predicting Classification

- Data from State Dept. Cables collection, 1973-1978
- Use Machine Learning techniques to predict the classification levels, which are tagged in the documents

TOP SECRET

TOP SECRET

FOR YOUR EYES ONLY

CONFIDENTIAL

CLASSIFIED

FOR YOUR EYES ONLY

Identifying features

- ① File Designation
- ② Action Distribution
- ③ Information Distribution
- ④ Security Classification
- ⑤ Airgram Number
- ⑥ Addressees
- ⑦ Originating Post
- ⑧ Preparation Date
- ⑨ Subject
- ⑩ References
- ⑪ Text

DEPT. DISTRIBUTION
ACTION
AGR-17

DEPARTMENT OF STATE
AIRGRAM AD(US)15-6 the Congo

Original to be Filed in _____ Declassified File: _____ FILE DESIGNATION

UNCLASSIFIED A-337

TO SECRETARY OF STATE FOR AGRICULTURE

FROM American Embassy, Kinshasa DATE September 14, 1966

SUBJECT PL AND Usual Marketing Requirement - Dairy Products

REF (1) A-18, September 6, 1966 (2) AGR-4, August 22, 1966

Report statistics are not available here which show breakdown between U.S. commercial sales and commercial shipments. However our check of figures submitted in ref. 2 indicates that if we subtract all U.S. shipments of any nature, the Congo still imported 1,931.1 metric tons of dairy products in the first half of FY 66. All non-U.S. shipments were commercial. Therefore Congo has completed its 1800 M.T. usual marketing requirement for dairy products. We assume no further information on this point is required.

FOR THE AMBASSADOR
John F. McMill
Acting Agricultural Attaché

UNCLASSIFIED

01000

Features	Description
<i>origclass</i>	The original class of the cable (the classification target)
<i>body</i>	Full text of the cable
<i>subject</i>	Keywords of subjects dealt with in the document.
<i>concepts</i>	Concepts attributed to the document
<i>TAGS</i>	Traffic Analysis by Geography and Subject
<i>from</i>	Who/where sent the document.
<i>to</i>	Who/where received the document.
<i>office</i>	Which State Department office or bureau sent the document.
<i>date</i>	Document creation date

(a) Training

(b) Prediction

Very ordinary results at first... ~0.75

- Simple classifiers → Neural Networks
- Scarce feature engineering → NLP and identification of named entities
- Few data cleansing → tap historians expertise

Exploring Temporal Evolution

Experiment:

- Split up cable collection if chunks of 5K cables
- Randomize the order
- Run a batch training on this set of batches

Predicting Failures on the Electrical System: the case of Light

Motivation

- FGV: Application of *Machine Learning* inspired by the [case of ConEdison](#)
- Light: Need to innovate in the management of underground cables structure

Goals

- Identify the risks of failure in the underground distribution network
- Predict the equipments with propension to failure and make forecasts
- Interpret collected data and models to help building regulation policies

Milestones

Data Collection

- Identification of the sources
- Data collections and Wrangling

Forecast Models

- Building Models and testing.
- Training and validation of the models
- Building reports and dashboards

Regulatory Policies

- Present the vision on how the regulation will change through technological transformations

DATA from the Systems

DATA from the equipments: IOT

Power Transformers in Rio de Janeiro

Power Transformers and Cables

The Methodology - CRISP-DM

Statistical Analysis of Data

AUTO KERAS

Neural Networks

Metodology: quick and dirty models (RF, XGBOOST)

(a) Training

(b) Prediction

Improving: LSTMs, AutoML + Keras

In [46]: `early_stopping = EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss', patience=3)`

```
history = model.fit(X_train,
                    y_train,
                    batch_size=batch_size,
                    epochs=epochs,
                    verbose=1,
                    validation_data=(X_test, y_test),
                    callbacks=[early_stopping])
```

Train on 60000 samples, validate on 10000 samples

```
Epoch 1/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 59s 991us/step - loss: 0.2632 - acc: 0.9195 - val_loss: 0.0
618 - val_acc: 0.9802
Epoch 2/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 61s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0901 - acc: 0.9733 - val_loss: 0.042
4 - val_acc: 0.9856
Epoch 3/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0664 - acc: 0.9801 - val_loss: 0.036
9 - val_acc: 0.9880
Epoch 4/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0543 - acc: 0.9837 - val_loss: 0.028
7 - val_acc: 0.9899
Epoch 5/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0476 - acc: 0.9854 - val_loss: 0.026
6 - val_acc: 0.9912
Epoch 6/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0424 - acc: 0.9874 - val_loss: 0.028
6 - val_acc: 0.9900
Epoch 7/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 63s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0378 - acc: 0.9886 - val_loss: 0.026
6 - val_acc: 0.9913
Epoch 8/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0345 - acc: 0.9894 - val_loss: 0.026
7 - val_acc: 0.9896
Epoch 9/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 63s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0327 - acc: 0.9902 - val_loss: 0.024
5 - val_acc: 0.9916
Epoch 10/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0308 - acc: 0.9903 - val_loss: 0.028
4 - val_acc: 0.9906
Epoch 11/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0296 - acc: 0.9909 - val_loss: 0.026
2 - val_acc: 0.9920
Epoch 12/12
60000/60000 [=====] - 62s 1ms/step - loss: 0.0271 - acc: 0.9919 - val_loss: 0.024
5 - val_acc: 0.9913
```

In [47]: `score = model.evaluate(X_test, y_test, verbose=1)`
`print('Test loss:', score[0])`
`print('Test accuracy:', score[1])`

```
10000/10000 [=====] - 4s 432us/step
Test loss: 0.024508397342383977
Test accuracy: 0.9913
```

Recall

58%
Initial

80%
Goal

72% +
Current

Precision

58%
Initial

80%
Goal

77% +
Current

Benefits

- Better services to the population
- *Data Science as part of the company operations*
- *Use of sensors and Internet of things for monitoring*
- International Benchmarking
 - *Technological Benchmarking*
 - *Regulatory Benchmarking*

Exploration Space @ ACDH

- Citizen science
- Citizen innovation
- Team Science
- Crowd research
- DYI science.

**Exploring Austrias
culture through the
language glass**

**ChIA – Accessing and
Analysing Images with
New Technologies**

**Progressive Visual
Decision-Making in
Digital Humanities**

Multidisciplinary team

Exploration Space @ ACDH

Motivation

- Foster scientific research on the frontiers of society, language and culture
- Create models (infrastructures, tools, processes) about the documentation, reuse and research of indigenous knowledge
- Trigger novel methods of experimentation against the background of citizen innovation and knowledge for development

Exploration Space @ ACDH

Goals

- Towards reinventing the genre: post-dictionary
- Creating a physical and virtual space for innovation and experimentation using new technologies (neural networks for image recognition and bias detection, network analysis, interactive visualization)
- Foster collaboration against the background of open innovation in science, methods and practices, offering relevant deliverables to the society.

Exploration Space @ ACDH

Milestones

- Knowledge design against open innovation in science
- Including citizens; citizen driven infrastructures and companies
- Data modeling including cultural perspective
- Data availability in RDF format - integration with LOD & Europeana
- Visual analytics dashboards
- Evaluation and aggregation of other data sets
- Analysis of workflows
- Metrics for experimentation and innovation
- Culturomics study
- Model for rethinking lexicography in a postdigital era

Semantic Technologies

Computer Vision

Chatbot

Europeana Image Collection

LOD (knowledge Graph)

Food Thesaurus

Rich technical and informational infrastructure

